

A Speech Act Analysis of the Speech of Nawaz Sharif Ex-Prime Minister of Pakistan

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 27, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: March 25, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Locutionary Act, Illocutionary Act, Perlocutionary Act, Speech Act Analysis, Direct & Indirect Speech Acts, Nawaz Sharif Ex- PM, Pakistan.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4637877</p>	<p><i>This paper aims to feature the speech acts which have been employed behind the speech that has delivered by Nawaz Sharif Ex-Prime Minister of Pakistan on September, 20th, 2020 through video link in a big public rally. The objective of this paper is to answer what kind of speech acts have been utilized, covering of what speech acts happened in Nawaz Sharif's discourse and what direct and indirect speech acts have been utilized.</i></p> <p><i>Theory and Method:</i> This paper-dependent on both qualitative and quantitative examination of talk. The structure used in this investigation is the Speech Act theory that has presented by J.L Austin in 1962 and further refined by J.R Searle (1969). Further, illocutionary acts that are used to achieve persuasion have also been seen. Hence, the data are characterised by a preponderance of assertive, expressive and commissive acts that are mostly used as mobilization strategies, especially in political campaigns, where it is essential for candidates to persuade their listeners to win elections or other political gains. <i>Results:</i> The findings uncovered his discourse incorporates representative acts (21.9%), expressive acts (11%), declarative acts (21.9%), directive acts (38.4%), commissive acts (5.5%) out of the complete 100% of data.</p>

Introduction

Individuals who communicate and produce the expressions that have words and syntactic structures and furthermore play out certain activities through those expressions that are considered to be as called speech acts. Discourse acts are commonly known as the demonstrations of correspondence and the demonstrations that are performed with expressions. The speech demonstration has its underlying foundations in crafted by Searle (1969) and Austin (1962). The discourse demonstration hypothesis might be depicted as "How to get communicative events done with words theory."

The purpose of this study is to explore the categories of speech acts, overlapping of the categories of speech acts, and direct and indirect speech acts that are working behind the historical political speech of Nawaz Sharif Ex-Prime Minister of Pakistan. Since, leaders of political parties are used different speeches during election and non-election situations to persuade their voters and supporters. The spoken communication is a mix of different direct and indirect speech acts according to the speech act theory.

As per Austin (1962), locutionary, illocutionary and perlocutionary are three types of speech acts. At the point when a speaker creates an expression, this demonstration of delivering that expression is called locutionary act. A regular power is carried out when a speaker creates or state that an expression, this is called illocutionary act. An impact on activities, sentiments and musings of audience members is known as the perlocutionary demonstration. Since the speeches that are delivered by politicians mainly concerned with making people believe what they are saying and the speech acts play the most significant role in it, by doing speech act analysis of political speeches of politician's researchers can come to know their intended meanings behind the speech. Speech Act theory was introduced by J.L Austin and further developed by Searle, and Bach and Harnish.

Safwat & Hashim (2015) stated that "political speech can be seen as a means of establishing and maintaining social relationships, expressing feelings, and selling ideas policies and programmes in any society." They further of the view that "political discourse is not only about stating public propositions. It is about politics. It is about doing things with words." The central point of speech act theory is based on illocutionary act that result perlocutionary effect on the listeners. The illocutionary act has been differentiated into five classes by Searle (1969). The inspiration behind this study is to research the characterizations of talk acts, covering of the classes of discourse acts, and prompt and winding speech acts that are working behind the widely covered and debated speech of Nawaz Sharif Ex-Prime Minister of Pakistan. Since the discussions that are passed on by government authorities essentially stressed over making people acknowledge what they are expressing and the

talk exhibits expect the primary capacity in it, by doing talk act examination of political discusses legislator's researchers can come to know their proposed ramifications behind the talk. By leading the discourse demonstration investigation of political talk, scientists can investigate the suggested implications and net of significant designs working behind the expressions of legislators. This paper expects to investigate these shrouded implications through the construction of the language used in this historic and widely covered and discussed speech of Nawaz Sharif.

1.1 Research Questions

RQ1. What types of speech acts have been used by Nawaz Sharif in his speech?

RQ2. Overlapping of what types of speech acts occurred in Nawaz Sharif's speech?

RQ3. What direct and indirect speech acts have been used by Nawaz Sharif?

1. Review of Literature:

Discourse Act hypothesis was presented by J.L Austin and further created via Searle, and Bach and Harnish. As indicated by Austin (1962), locutionary, illocutionary and perlocutionary are three classes of discourse acts. At the point when a speaker delivers an expression, this demonstration of creating that expression is guest locutionary act. An ordinary power is accomplished when a speaker creates or state that an expression, this is called illocutionary act. An impact on activities, sentiments and musings of audience members is known as the perlocutionary demonstration.

“Speech act theory is a subfield of pragmatics that studies how words are used not only to present information but also to carry out actions” (Richard Nordquist, 2020). The structure utilized in this investigation is the Speech Act hypothesis that has been given by J.L Austin in 1962, and afterward it has been additionally evolved via Searle (1969). The specialist has utilized the discourse demonstration examination to direct the subjective investigation of choosing fifty expressions of political discourse in light of the fact that it is conceivable to investigate his concealed expectations and perspectives of the speaker. Quantitatively, the results have been presented in a simple central tendency.

A large quantity of research has been witnessed on the speeches of prominent politicians of the world. Different methods and theoretical lines have been used like critical discourse analysis, systemic functional linguistics, check list models and political linguistics etc. Mostly such studies are based on race, racism, identity, etc. US President Ronald Regan's discourse was conveyed on socialism to the people of the West Berlin and the world. The discourse, 'Destroy this Wall' was conveyed against the foundation of the social and cultural history of the Americans and it completes in the kick-off of the Berlin divider. The study examined and analysed the value of Regan's powerful utilization of language in empowering the kick-off of the Berlin divider. Bullock (2003) analysed the logical techniques utilized by President Bush as methods for influence for the justification of the Iraqi's war and to legitimize America's advantage in indicting the war (Skoniecki and College, 2004).

Cook,(1992) speech act theory tells the path and guidelines for digging deep into the discourse and describing the meaning of what is said. In other words, this theory tries to explore how speakers use words to get intended responses and how listeners conclude intended meaning from the spoken words. Levinson (1983) states: performatives are, if one likes, just rather special sorts of ceremony. And unlike constative, which are assessed in terms of truth and falsify, performatives can only be assessed as felicitous or infelicitous, according to whether their felicity conditions are met or not.

In 1930s, there was a belief that unless the sentence can be verified, it is meaningless. This was based on the doctrine of "Logical Positivism" where most of the ethical, aesthetic and literary discourses and everyday utterances were simply meaningless (Altikriti, 2011). Discourse Act hypothesis was presented by J.L Austin and further created via Searle, and Bach and Harnish. As indicated by Austin (1962), locutionary, illocutionary and perlocutionary are three classes of discourse acts. At the point when a speaker delivers an expression, this demonstration of creating that expression is guest locutionary act. An ordinary power is accomplished when a speaker creates or state that an expression, this is called illocutionary act. An impact on activities, sentiments and musings of audience members is known as the perlocutionary demonstration. Most politicians are ignorant of the way that there is a connection between what have said, what have meant, what conveyed by the activity passed on by what is said (Safwat & Hashim, 2015). They further argued that:

“In political speeches, ideas and ideologies need to be conveyed through language so that they are agreed upon by the receivers as well as by others who may read or hear parts of the speech afterwards in the media. Words and expressions are used or omitted to affect meaning in different ways.”

Rudyk (2007) has inspected the discourse of George W. Bush and the power relations in his discourse. The discourse contemplated the maltreatment of power in America and the Iraqi war and considered its impact on the beneficiaries. In political science, the Danish capital college adopts human activity as a style of felicitous human activity (or merely 'facilitating conditions'), whereby the speaker, typically politicians or sports men, act in accordance to the reality however in preparation for the audience to require action within the directions of the

player that area unit driven or incited by the act. This forms associate noticeable framework under a specific subject material from the player, and therefore the audience unit 'under-theorised [would] stay outside of the framework itself, and would take pleasure in being each brought in and drawn out (McDonald, 2008)."In speech act theory, the hearer is seen as playing a passive role. The illocutionary force of a particular utterance is determined with regard to the linguistic form of the utterance and also introspection as to whether the necessary felicity conditions not least in relation to the speaker's beliefs and feelings are fulfilled. Interactional aspects are, thus, neglected. However, [a] conversation is not just a mere chain of independent illocutionary forces rather, speech acts are related to other speech acts with a wider discourse context."Barron (2003).

3. Theoretical underpinnings: Theory of speech act that has presented by J.L Austin (How to Do Things with Words, 1962), and it was further established by J.R Searle (1969). This theory is central to logic and in order to interpret the meanings and explanations of words that does work in different speeches can only be analysed and interpreted by this important tool called speech act theory. By using words various actions can perform through words or a specific act is done when utterances are being utilized these can be called as speech acts.

As per Austin (1962), there are three parts of speech acts that are: locutionary act (the creation of significant etymological articulation), illocutionary act(there is in every case some sort of activity in an expression that we structure, and an expression has an open power and an illocutionary demonstration is performed by that open power of an expression), perlocutionary act(an expression affects the sentiments, contemplations and mentalities of an audience that impact is known as the perlocutionary demonstration, so it is an impact of an expression). As per Searle, five classes of illocutionary act that are clarified as:

1. **Representatives:** These are the sorts of speech acts, that give speakers to state what he/she accepts to be the situation or not. It uses action words, for example, a report, finishes up, denies, accepts and insists.
2. **Expressive:** These are those sorts of speech acts that educate us concerning speaker's disposition, mental state by using action words, for example, lament, welcome, thank, praise, loathe, appreciate, hate.
3. **Directive:** When speakers need another person to carry out something, they perform mandate discourse act by using words, for example, welcome, demand, order, ask, challenge, ask, dare, and demand.
4. **Commissive:** When speakers need to concede to some future activities, they perform commissive discourse acts, with action words, for example, vow, swear, warrant, pledge, guarantee, ensure, attempt.
5. **Declarations:** These speech demonstrations can change the world through expressions; the speaker can modify the state of a circumstance by making the expression. For instance, I articulate you a couple.

As indicated by Austin (1962), speech acts have additionally arranged based on their constructions; these are objective, revelatory and inquisitive discourse acts. Speech acts might be immediate and circuitous. When there is an immediate connection among ability and construction of speech acts, they are called direct speech acts. On the other hand, when there is an indirect connection between structure and function of discourse acts, these are called indirect speech acts.

2. Methodology:

Qualitative and quantitative approaches have been used in this research study to measure the speech act phenomenon. The researchers have gone through the data which have been selected from the first speech in a series of speeches of Nawaz Sharif, ex-Prime Minister which has been delivered through video link on September, 20th 2020, in connection with protests organized by opposition against the sitting government of Imran Khan. The agenda of these protests was to highlight the bad governance, corruption, inflation, national sovereignty, economic downfall, and foreign front failures with ultimate aim to topple down the government. The speech has translated into English and highlighted around 83 utterances. The researchers have selected those specific 83 utterances in which the speaker Mr. Nawaz Sharif has been discussed all the big challenges and failures of the sitting government before the nation on live coverage via video link from London.

Data Collection: The script of this address of Nawaz Sharif on 20th, Sep 2020 was downloaded from the internet. This live speech was delivered after the construction of Pakistan Democratic Movement (an alliance of opposition political parties) in the rally arranged at Gujranwala a city of Punjab province. The speech was welcomed by supporters of democratic process in Pakistan and it enjoys a historical importance. Basic speech act theory was applied to realize the discourse demonstrations.

3. Data Analysis:

The researchers of this study have additionally given a clarification of about those fifty expressions in data examination as per the classes of discourse and speech acts. In the following Section-I is highlighted the speech act investigation quantitatively by its utterances in a sequel manner.

Direct and Indirect Speech Acts

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
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Valid	Representatives	16	21.9	22.2	22.2
	Declaratives	16	21.9	22.2	44.4
	Commissive	4	5.5	5.6	50.0
	Expressive	8	11.0	11.1	61.1
	Directive	28	38.4	38.9	100.0
	Total	72	98.6	100.0	
Missing	System	1	1.4		
	Total	73	100.0		

Table 1

Table 1 illustrates that 16 out of total 72 speech acts are fall in representative class, 16 speech acts are turned as declarative, 4 speech acts are taken as commissive class, and 8 out of total 72 speech acts are expressive while 28 speech acts are turned as directive used by Nawaz Sharif in his widely covered and debated speech.

Therefore, he has used 21.9% speech acts as representative, again 21.9% speech acts are declarative, 4% acts are commissive speech acts, 8% speech acts are expressive, and 38.4% speech acts are directive speech acts.

Fig1

Fig 1 above shows that 72 times direct speech acts have been used in the sample exclamations of Nawaz Sharif's speech. Out of these acts, 30 are direct directive, 24 declarative, 11 representative and 4 commissive and 3 expressive. Therefore, direct speech acts have taken place as 41.6% direct directive, 33.3% direct declarative, 15.2% direct representative speech acts, 5.5% commissive, 4.1% direct expressive speech acts. 86.7% are counted as direct speech acts.

Fig2

Fig 2 above proves that indirect declarative and indirect representative got 27.2% indirect speech acts. Indirect directive and indirect commissive acts were counted as 18.18 each. 9% was gone to indirect expressive speech acts.

1. "Starting with the name of Allah, I am thankful to Mr. Asif Ali Zardari, BilawalZardari, Molana Fazal-Ur-Rehman, Muhammad Shahbaz Sharif, Ms. Maryam Nawaz, Achakzai sahib, and other prominent leaders."(expressive, directive, illocutionary act)
2. "I am far from my country, but I can understand the problems of my compatriots. Now the time has come and telling us to abandon all expediency and move towards the goal of democracy". (representative, directive, illocutionary act) In these two sentences, there are two class levels. The first class is representative while the second class denotes to directive.
3. "In the light of my vast experience, I can say that Pakistan has been kept away from the democratic system and this is the reason for the destruction of Pakistan". (directive, declarative, commissive, illocutionary act)
4. "Public opinion is respected and valued all over the world. And when the dignity of the vote is violated, the nation bears this loss." (directive, direct representative, declarative, warning, illocutionary act)
5. "Before the election, it is decided who will win and who will lose. This is how the desired results are achieved." (indirect, declarative, directive, illocutionary act)
6. "The deficit is taken out by the buying of parliamentarians and the mandate of the public is stolen in this way." (indirect, directive, illocutionary act)

7. "In the seventy-seven-year history of the country, an elected Prime Minister was allowed to complete his term." (indirect, directive, declarative, illocutionary act)
8. "Each dictator ruled for nine years in average, while the elected representatives of the nation were given two years in average." (directive, declarative, illocutionary act)
9. "When the general who broke the constitution twice was summoned by the court, the apex court gave him a certificate of innocence." (directive, illocutionary act)
10. "The apex court gave the dictator a certificate to play with." (directive, commissive, illocutionary act)
11. "You know how a democratic government is discredited. How public representatives are humiliated, how they are imprisoned in false cases, and how criticism of policy is turned into treason?" (indirect, representative, directive, illocutionary act)
12. "The bottom line here is that either there is martial-law, or a parallel government is more powerful than the people's government. Pakistan has been placed as a laboratory for such experiments" (indirect, representative, declarative, directive, illocutionary act)
13. "Now, the matter has gone beyond the 'state within the state' and reached at the 'state above the state' and that's the root of all problems." (directive, warning, illocutionary act)
14. "Can I dare to ask if why RTS was put on hold on the day of election? Why polling agents were evacuated during the count?" (declarative, expressive, warning, directive, illocutionary act)
15. "The election was rigged, at whose request. The Election Commissioner and the Secretary Election Commissioner will have to answer." (directive, representative, declarative, warning, command, illocutionary act)
16. "Ten million jobs have been swindled and the employers have taken back more than 10 million jobs." (indirect, representative, directive, illocutionary act)
17. "Non-borrowers have won all the records of borrowing and Pakistan has been mortgaged." (indirect, declarative, directive, warning, illocutionary act)
18. "In 2018, world's financial Institutions around the world were predicting that Pakistan would jump into the rapidly growing economies in the next few years." (direct representative, belief and illocutionary act)
19. "I want to make it clear that if the vote is not respected then we will not be able to defend our homeland." (commissive, declarative, directive, illocutionary act)
20. "The power to formulate foreign policy rests solely with the elected government." (declarative, commanding, illocutionary act)
21. "In the last seventy-three years, Kashmir has not been ruled by India, but today India has taken advantage of Pakistan's puppet government to make Kashmir a part of India." (indirect, directive, warning, illocutionary act)
22. "Today our old friends have walked away from us. Why we are suffering from international loneliness?" (declarative, warning, commissive, illocutionary act) asking a question.
23. "The Chinese President's visit was postponed due to a sit-in to thwart the CPEC plan." (warning, directive, illocutionary act)
24. "The International Court of Justice and Pakistani courts have accused the NAB of being suspicious and dishonest towards the people who criticise the government. In other words, this institution has become

so stinking that it is impossible to support it.” (expressive, representative, declarative, warning, directive, illocutionary act)

25. “Whoever is released from NAB is handed over to FIA, and whoever is released from FIA is handed over to anti-narcotics and whoever escapes anti-narcotics is caught in another false case.” (directive, warning, illocutionary act)
26. Aleema Khan who is a modern backbencher who just keeps on fundraising for charities, where will the NAB deal with the assets of the billionaires. Will there be any JIT on the money trail of hundreds of kanals of land of Bunni Gala? (representative, warning, directive, illocutionary act) Asking a question.
27. Will NAB examine the expenses incurred by Imran Khan's Bunny Galla and Zaman Park Lahore bungalows? (direct, declarative, directive, representative, commissive, illocutionary act) Asking a question.
28. “Let decide today do we want to leave a Pakistan for future generations where justice and Judges Sell. I would say never, never, never.” (representative, declarative, warning, directive, illocutionary act)
29. “I have already made it clear that our fight is not with Imran Khan but with those who brought Imran Khan through vote theft.” (Command, declarative, warning, directive, illocutionary act)
30. We have made this country an atomic power and today we want the country's armed forces to be strong. (direct, declarative, representative, expressive, illocutionary act)
31. “Leadership of the armed forces should keep themselves away from politics in the framework of the constitution of Pakistan and advices of Jinnah.” (Command, warning, directive, locutionary act)
32. “Don't jump on the wall of the Prime Minister's House and arrest the Prime Minister at gunpoint.” (direct, representative, declarative, warning, expressive, locutionary, act)
33. “There are as many restrictions on the media today as there were martial law. Journalists today cannot write the truth.” (direct, representative, warning, expressive, locutionary, act)
34. “I assure you that my party will stand by all the decisions of Pakistan Democratic Movement (PDM).” (declarative, expressive, commissive, representative, illocutionary act)
35. I thank Bilawal Bhutto Zardari, the host of the PDM meeting, for giving me the opportunity to present my case. (expressive, representative, illocutionary act)

4. Discussion and Conclusion

The researchers have explored the simultaneously use of the all the five classes of speech acts in the political speech of Nawaz Sharif live from London through a video link. They further examined the direct and indirect classes, and different types of speech acts the speaker has used. On the basis of speech act theory presented by Austin and refined by Searle, the researchers have analysed the data and explored that out of total 72 speech acts, speaker has used illocutionary acts frequently as he used direct directive acts 30 times while direct declarative acts 24 times in his speech. The other significant classes which Nawaz Sharif avoided was direct commissive and direct expressive 4 and 3 times, respectively. Direct representative type was used 11 times. Nawaz Sharif never focused on future commitments on present and past. He has used 11 indirect illocutionary acts on the same pattern that occurred in direct speech acts. The results show that direct speech acts have been remained dominant in this political speech. Nawaz Sharif has used directive and declarative acts so often which shows his command and vibrancy. Directive speech acts were used to mobilize supporters and to provoke actions that were ultimate goal of this association called Pakistan democratic movement.

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